

HP sintering of yttrium-aluminate glass-Impact of particle size distribution on mechanical properties

^{1,2}Anna Prnová, ^{1,2}Jana Valuchová, ³Žaneta Dohnalová, ⁴Ondrej Hanzel, ²Robert Klement, ⁵Els Bruneel, ^{1,2}Dušan Galusek

¹Join Glass Centre of the IIC SAS, TnUAD, FChPT STU, Študentská 2, 911 50
Trenčín, Slovakia

²FunGlass, A. Dubček University of Trenčín, Študentská 2, 911 50 Trenčín, Slovakia

³Institute of Inorganic Chemistry, Slovak Academy of Sciences, Dúbravska cesta 9, 845 36
Bratislava, Slovak Republic

⁴Department of Inorganic Technology, Faculty of Chemical Technology, University of
Pardubice, Doubravice 41, 532 10 Pardubice, Czech Republic

⁵Department of Inorganic and Physical Chemistry, Gent University, Krijgslaan 281 (53), 9000
Gent, Belgium

Email: anna.prnova@tnuni.sk

The samples AYEM, AYEMB and AYEMFD, containing 76.8 mol.% Al_2O_3 and 23.2 mol.% Y_2O_3 were prepared by three different ways. The combination of modified Pechini sol-gel method and flame synthesis was used for preparation of AYEM sample. The prepared glass microspheres (AYEM) were subsequently ground in vibratory mill (Fritsch Pulverisette 0) for 30, 45, 60, 75, 90, 105, 120, 150, 180, 210 and 240 min with amplitude 1.0 mm and marked as samples AYEBM1-AYEBM11. For preparation of AYEMFD sample, the combination of sol-gel Pechini method, freeze-drying and flame synthesis was used. All prepared systems were studied by using of XRD, DTA, PSA and SEM analysis. Preliminary HP and RHP experiments were performed. The Vickers hardness 16.6 – 17.0 GPa was obtained in sintered samples. The morphology of prepared glass-ceramics materials were examined by scanning electron microscopy and the results are reported.

Fig.1. SEM images of AYEM sample (a), grinding sample AYEBM11 (b) and freeze-dried sample AYEMFD (c).

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